
Fashion Trend Forecasting Spirituality as an Inspiration in Creating Evening Party Dress Design Illustration Titled De Valeur

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Abstract

De Valeur comes from the French word which means "Precious" and is the title of a work of evening dress design illustration which take an inspiration from by 2021/2022 fashion trend forecasting theme : Spirituality. Spirituality being depicted by the use of Indonesian traditional fabric which is woven fabric that becomes one of the idea for creating evening party dress design illustration. This is based on the fact that the Spirituality theme has characteristics such as classic and elegant impression, colors that tend to be earth tones, the use of natural materials, or even the use of traditional fabrics. The aim of this creation is to describe the process and the result of creating an evening party dress design illustration which applies fashion trend forecasting theme as an inspiration. This creation using the practice-led research method of craft arts, consisting of 4 stages which includes: (1) pre-design, (2) design, (3) Embodiment, and (4) presentation. The results of this research shows the process of creating evening dress design illustration which includes exploring idea, developing alternative designs, perfecting the chosen design and publishing the illustration which in line with practice-led method stages order. The result of this research is 1 piece of evening dress fashion design illustration front and back look titled "De Valeur" designed and inspired by the characteristics from Fashion Trend Forecasting Spirituality.

Keywords: design illustration, party dress, fashion trend forecasting

Abstrak

“De Valeur” berasal dari kata Perancis yang berarti "Berharga" dan merupakan judul dari sebuah karya ilustrasi desain busana pesta malam yang mengambil inspirasi dari tema fashion trend forecasting 2021/2022 : Spirituality. Spirituality dicerminkan dengan penggunaan kain

tradisional Indonesia yaitu kain tenun yang menjadi salah satu inspirasi dalam membuat ilustrasi desain gaun pesta malam. Hal ini berdasarkan pada tema Spiritualitas memiliki karakteristik seperti kesan klasik dan elegan, warna yang cenderung earth tone, penggunaan bahan-bahan alami, atau bahkan penggunaan kain tradisional. Tujuan penciptaan ini antara lain untuk mendeskripsikan proses dan hasil penciptaan ilustrasi desain busana pesta malam berjudul “De Valeur” yang menerapkan fashion trend forecasting Spirituality dalam acuan inspirasinya. Penciptaan ini menggunakan metode practice-led research seni kriya, yang terdiri dari 4 tahap yang meliputi (1) pra-perancangan, (2) perancangan, (3) perwujudan, dan (4) penyajian. Hasil penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa proses dari penciptaan ilustrasi desain busana pesta malam yang meliputi eksplorasi sumber ide, membuat desain alternatif, perwujudan karya hingga publikasi karya sesuai dengan urutan teori practice-led research Seni Kriya. Hasil penciptaan berupa 1 karya ilustrasi desain busana pesta malam berjudul “De Valeur” yang didesain sesuai karakteristik trend forecasting Spirituality dengan tampilan tampak depan dan belakang.

Kata Kunci: Ilustrasi desain, busana pesta, fashion trend forecasting.

Introduction

Indonesian Trend Forecasting (ITF) is a research group whose membership is formed from a collection of fashion designers and other practitioner experts who have the goal of assisting the government in advancing the development of the creative economy in the fashion sector in Indonesia (Santika, et al. 2021). ITF explores creative ideas from industry players in the fields of fashion, textiles, interiors, and products with the aim of advancing Indonesia's creative industry motivated by research and trends for artisans and more in the fashion sector in exploring visuals and new ideas for market trends. With the hope of the outcome being more of innovative products that continue to sell well in the market and the wheels of the economy will spin so that the surrounding community will also prosper (Aninda and Setyawan 2022).

Indonesian Fashion Trend launches a theme for Trend Forecasting every year. In 2021, Indonesia Trend Forecasting launched a Fashion Trend 2021/2022 book, "The New Beginning", a direction or trend foothold for the fashion and textile sector. "The New Beginning" has the meaning of a life or a new beginning. This theme was made by reflecting lives of people that affected by the pandemic so that the theme displayed is a depiction of hope in entering a new era. There are four subthemes in "The New Beginning" which consist of; Essentiality, Spirituality, Exploitation, and Exploration.

Spirituality is a theme that rests on awareness in protecting nature and culture. The theme is inspired by the classic side with earthy colors, the use of natural materials and the usage of many details and characteristics such as fringe, unfinished edge, pleats drapery and macramé (Indonesia Trend Forecasting, 2021). The theme is such an opportunity for fashion students and designers from all over the region, to creates fashion artwork such as fashion design collection in the form of a participation in preserving local wisdom but also based on trends. According to Amos et al. (2017), Fashion design can potentially attract the attention

of its viewers which is made through a variety of inspirational media in a neat and creative way. Creating fashion arts but applying the theme that exists in trend forecasting especially Spirituality is a challenge that can support the birth of many creative ideas of students and fashion designers.

Fashion designing is an artwork that is arranged by paying attention to lines, shapes, colors, sizes and textures so that they become one in order to produce a beautiful and attractive clothing visual (Yuliati & Asri, 2015). Fashion illustration is the earliest work in the steps of fashion designing before entering other steps. The work in its creation also tends to be easier and appealing. The fashion design illustration itself is a fashion design that is visualized in various ways. In making fashion design illustrations, there are several techniques such as manual, digital, and combination techniques where the differences can be seen from the tools and materials used in the manufacturing process (Diantari & Kadek, 2022). Before creating fashion works, mainly designers need to get some source of idea. According to Rizkiya, et al. (2023) A source of ideas is something that functions to support the creative and planning stages of a design. And in this case, Spirituality theme can be used as source of idea.

In woman fashion there is such wide range of occasion. From a formal, casual into certain event occasion. Especially, in event occasion the design can be so diverse. According to Marniati (2012:13) Party clothes generally have certain characteristics that distinguish them from everyday clothes. Party clothes themselves are clothes worn to attend important activities and each can be distinguished based on the time attending such as in morning, afternoon and night with their own characteristics and made with special sewing technique (Rizqi & Maeliah, 2020). Due to its diversity and special characteristics, party occasion clothing can be seen as an opportunity to create a special and authentic fashion design. In creating a party occasion fashion design, pouring creative ideas is indispensable to create a fashion design. Ideas can be drawn from various things with examples such as the eras of fashion, trends, events that have occurred and the forms in the surrounding nature (Agustini et al, 2018).

In creating a work or collection of works, it must be based on creation method which consist creation steps. The creation of artworks has various theories, techniques and method in the process of creating artworks. For an example, a practice-led research method of craft arts which consists of 4 stages of creation. Namely, Pre-Design, Design, Embodiment and Presentation of the work (Hendriyana, 2021). Practice-led research method is one of the many methods that can be applied by researchers and designers in the process of creating artworks in fashion. Based on the description above, the researcher had the opportunity to create an illustration of an evening party dress design illustration entitled "De Valeur" using the practice-led method. The purpose of this creation is to describe the process and results of the creation of the "De Valeur" design illustration.

Research Method

This research was used by the researcher to find out the process of creating a monumental work of party fashion design illustration that applies fashion trend forecasting with the theme of fashion trend forecast spirituality. The creation of the evening dress design illustration with the title "De Valeur" uses the method of Practice-led research method of craft arts. Which the method consists of 4 stages, including: (a) Pre-Design; (b) Design ; (c) Embodiment; and (d) Presentation (Hendriyana, 2021).

Pre-design is the stage where the researcher explores the source of relevant ideas or issues in the field. At this stage, the researcher collecting some ideas and pour them into one media such as plan board or moodboard. Design is the stage of visualizing the source of idea. By realizing these visual ideas, a prototype or alternative designs is created with aspects of consideration of values, functions and meanings. The Embodiment stage is the continuation of visualization and perfecting the design to adjust its meaning, value and function based on ideas that have been prepared. The presentation stage is the stage where the artwork is published.

Results and Discussion

In the pre-design stage, the researcher explores the source of ideas or relevant issues in the field. At this stage, the researcher develops his imagination and ideas by rationalizing with various references and similar works. Thus, at this stage it produces moodboards and basic design based on trend forecasting theme Spirituality. The moodboard being used as source of ideas to create evening party dress fashion designs. Moodboards are visual media used to collect and display inspiration, ideas, and concepts in fashion design or other designs. (Tanaya, et al. 2022).

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The moodboard above was a moodboard for “De Valeur” source of idea. It consisting evening dress silhouette, depiction Spirituality characteristics such as earthy tone color, pleats detail, drapery, unfinished edge, fringe and usage of traditional or cultural motifs referencing from Indonesian woven fabrics. And picture below was two basic evening party dress design that is having L and I line silhouette.

Furthermore, at this stage of design, the researcher made 5 alternative design illustrations developed from the initial basic design by applying elements on the moodboard wich consisting sources of ideas, and characteristics on the Spirituality theme. designing is the stage where the researcher creating and develop the fashion design that based on the main reference (Afidah & Russanti, 2022). Here are the results of 5 illustrations of “De Valeur” alternative designs that have been designed using the spirituality themed moodboard as the reference.

Alternative design is assessed by 2 experts in fashion design to select the main design that will get continued as a complete and finished illustration. The alternative designs judged based on some aspects in fashion. Apart from the creativity aspect, it is explained in Arifiana et al, (2018) there is also 3 important aspects in clothing, including: (a) functional; (b) expression; and (c) aesthetics. The main design being selected based on the accumulation of the largest points using scoring instruments in which there are functional, creative and aesthetic aspects to be valued each design.

Table 1 Alternative Designs Scoring

Alternative Design	Design Expert 1	Design Expert 2	Total Score
1.	86	82	168
2.	86	89	175
3.	96	95	191
4.	87	92	179
5.	76	75	151

The table above shows the accumulated assesment score from the five existing alternative designs and shows that the design with the number 3 has the most points in terms of functional, creativity, and aesthetic aspects. so it can be concluded that alternative design 3 will proceed into the embodiement stage.

At the realization stage, in accordance with the technique of making design illustrations which can consist of: (a) making proportions, (b) making proportional features, (c) designing fashion shapes, (d) detailing and finally (e) finishing. (Bryant, 2008). The work "De Valeur" will be made using a manual technique with wet and dry coloring techniques, so the process can be described below:

- a) Preparing tools and materials
- b) Making figures or proportions of women
- c) Drawing the design of the "De Valeur" party fashion shape
- d) Coloring figures and designs according to the characteristics of spiritual coloring by dry technique with colored pencils and then combined with wet techniques using watercolors.
- e) Detailing the visualization of the of woven fabric motifs
- f) Sharpen the details, decorate and finishing the illustration.

The result of the illustration design "De Valeur" :

Description:

"De Valeur" is the title of an illustration of evening party dress design which means "Precious". This is based on the essence of the use of the dominance of Indonesian woven fabric motifs. The result of the "De Valeur" design illustration is a complete evening party dress with a front and back view.

The characteristics of an evening party dress are displayed through the shape of the dress with having L line silhouette and displayed in the form of a long one-piece dress. The dress was shown with several elements of details that reflect the characteristics of trend forecasting spirituality theme. The characteristics of spirituality are displayed through several elements such as the majority use of earthy color and classic tones, the use of fringe details and unfinished edges on several parts, drapery accents on the waist and the bustier, pleated accents on the shape of the sleeves, and the use of the Indonesian traditional woven fabric motif as in majority of the fabric materials. This design is in line with the main goal of spirituality, which is to preserve local culture and wisdom.

Finally, at the stage of presentation or dissemination of this work, it is a process with the aim of communicative, complementary and elaboration of works that are made in one direction according to the target of creation, the researcher publishing through to social media post as an online art exhibition and article publications.

In this case, the artwork being published in social media Instagram with link : <https://www.instagram.com/p/CW7FKUHP8gk/?igsh=dDQxbXh1cHh5cTBn> .

Conclusion

The process of creating “De Valeur” evening party fashion design illustrations is done in accordance with the practice-led research method of craft arts which consists of pre-design, design, Embodiment and presentation. the pre-design process shown by exploring the source of ideas through the theme of trend forecasting spirituality which resulting of moodboard and basic design, in the design stage the researcher visualized the source of ideas by developing and designing alternative designs, at the embodiment stage by perfecting the visualization of chosen alternative design with fashion illustration techniques, and finally at the stage of presenting the work by publishing the work in several publication media.

The result of this creation is a piece of evening party dress fashion design illustration workpiece titled “De Valeur” front and back look. The design work displays the characteristics of evening dress with the shape of a long one-piece dress with a L line silhouette. Spirituality theme characteristics are shown and applied to the design by using the dominance of woven fabric motifs, the dominance use of classic earthy colors, the use of details such as pleat accents, fringe, drapery and unfinished edges.

References

- Afidah & Russanti. (2022). Faktor Eksternal Yang Mempengaruhi Kreativitas Mendesain Busana. *Jurnal Online Tata Busana*, 11(2) 137-153. doi:10.26740/jotb.v11n2.p137-153
- Agustini Agustini, I. Gede Sudirtha, and Made Diah Angendari. 2019. “Pengembangan Busana Pesta Malam Dengan Sumber Ide Dari Mitologi Kerajaan Yunani.” *Jurnal BOSAPARIS: Pendidikan Kesejahteraan Keluarga* 9(3):222. doi: 10.23887/jjpkk.v9i3.22152.
- Amos, E., Osei-Poku,P., Ahiabor, R. and Peligah, Y.S. (2017). *Exploring Digital Techniques for Fashion Illustration*. ADRRI Journal of Arts and Social Sciences, Ghana: Vol. 15,

No. 5 (3), Pp. 1-16, E-ISSN: 2343-6891, 30th November, 2017.

- Aninda, Nafisa, and Setyawan. (2022). "Kajian Trend Forecasting Ready To Wear Indonesia Trend Forecasting (Itf) 2019/2020 Sebagai Pendukung Kebijakan Badan Ekonomi Kreatif (Bekraf)." *Center Of Education Journal (CEJou)* 2(01):48–62. doi: 10.55757/cejou.v2i01.17.
- Arifiana, Simatupang, and Gustami. (2018). "PAKAIAN SERAGAM PERAWAT: SEBUAH RANCANGAN PENELITIAN." *CORAK Jurnal Seni Kriya* Vol. 7 No.1. doi:10.24821/corak.v7i1.2649
- Asri Nurbaeti Santika, Eneng Lutfia Zahra, and Dewi Suliyanthini. (2021). "Fashion Forecaster Sebagai Penentu Trend." *Practice of Fashion and Textile Education Journal* 1(2):35–47. doi: 10.21009/pftej.v1i2.26105.
- Hendriyana, H. (2021). *Metodologi enelitian penciptaan karya: practice-led research and practice-based research*. Andi.
- Indonesia Trend Forecasting. (2021). *"The New Beginning"*. Jakarta.
- Marniati. (2012). *Modul Busana Wanita*. UNESA. Surabaya.
- Michele Wesen Bryant. (2011). *Fashion Drawing: Illustration Techniques for Fashion Designers*. Laurance King Publishing. UK.
- Rizkiya, Amaliya Lailatur, Yulistiana Yulistiana, and Indarti Indarti. (2023). "Bunga Lavatera Sebagai Sumber Ide Penciptaan Busana Pesta." *BAJU: Journal of Fashion and Textile Design Unesa* 3(2):48–56. doi: 10.26740/baju.v3n2.p48-56.
- Rizqi, V.P., & Maeliah, M. (2020). Eksplorasi Bordir Motif Bunga Sebagai Decorative Trims Pada Busana Pesta. *Jurnal Da Moda*, 2(1), 1-6. doi:10.35886/damoda.v2i1.106
- Tanaya, Luh Maharani, Putu Agus Mayuni, and Made Diah Angendari. (2022). "Pengembangan Media Moodboard Pada Mata Pelajaran Desain Busana Untuk Siswa Kelas Xi Smk Negeri 1 Seririt." *Jurnal BOSAPARIS: Pendidikan Kesejahteraan Keluarga* 13(1):11–19. doi: 10.23887/jppkk.v13i1.43786.
- Yuni Diantari, Ni Kadek. (2022). "Pembelajaran Ilustrasi Fashion Digital Berbasis Kearifan Lokal Di Program Studi Desain Mode Institut Seni Indonesia Denpasar." *Segara Widya Jurnal Penelitian Seni* 10(1):57–64. doi: 10.31091/sw.v10i1.1935.
- Yuliati, Nanie Asri. (2015). "Peningkatan Kreativitas Seni Dalam Desain Busana." *Imaji* 5(2). doi: 10.21831/imaji.v5i1.6681